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Glance into the Future: Research Steps on a Path to a Continuous Human Presence on Moon, Mars and Beyond

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Abstract. Humans have been present in space for five decades and the dream of travelling and exploring space is even older. The next major step after a prolonged human presence on low Earth orbit is a prolonged human presence on other solar system bodies like Moon, Mars or even beyond. Since mid-2011 one research field of the System Analysis Space Segment (SARA) department of DLR has been the establishment of human outposts in the form of space habitats. This paper aims to showcase these activities and summarize their most important results in three primary branches. First, the design of a facility for the integrated testing and qualification of habitat technology on Earth. Second, one of the department's core competencies: Space greenhouse technology. This paper explains which steps, from concept over breadboard to laboratory work, eventually led to the current design, construction and operation of a space greenhouse analogue in Antarctica as well as the relevance for future space missions. The third branch, mainly intended to bolster the theoretical work with more practical insight into habitat design and operation are the analogue test site missions conducted by the department in 2013 and 2014. It is explained how these missions helped with the design and devel-

opment of the current hardware projects and the future research facility.

1 Introduction

For more than fifty years, humans have been present in space and the dream of travelling and exploring space is even older. The next major step after an extended human presence on low Earth orbit is an extended or even continuous human presence on other solar system bodies like Moon, Mars or even beyond.

Since mid-2011 one research field of the System Analysis Space Segment (SARA) department of DLR has been the establishment of human outposts in the form of space habitats. This paper aims to showcase these activities and summarize their most important results in three primary branches.

First, the design of a facility for the integrated testing and qualification of habitat technology on Earth. This proto-habitat's main purpose is not the analogous simulation of any kind of human mission to another celestial body, but to allow high-fidelity and continuous validation and integrated testing of habitat technology of various domains, e.g. life support, in-situ resource utilization and power. The current preliminary design is based

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on calculations of material fluxes (e.g. oxygen, hydrogen, carbon) within the habitat in various forms (water, CO₂) to determine the rate of success regarding a closed loop of 100% .

The facility is based on a modular approach, where single modules exist and execute certain functions (e.g. acting as greenhouse) and are also modularly built themselves, i.e. parts of each subsystem can be exchanged for testing and further development. Depending largely on the amount of funding for such a research facility, further simulation oriented system parts can be included, e.g. a dome structure for EVA simulations and so on. Furthermore the design takes into account the needs of a human crew, including — as best as possible — comforts for the crew.

Besides the direct application for research on space capable technology, this facility is suitable for improving technology standards on Earth ensuring a reduction of environmental footprint and enabling more efficient urban habitation. Due to the high demand for efficient resource utilization in space, this facility can act as driver for the development for “greener” technologies on Earth at the same time.

The second branch of research presented in this paper focuses on one of the department’s core competencies: Space greenhouse technology. Plant cultivation in large-scale closed environments is challenging and several key technologies necessary for space-based plant production are not yet space-qualified or remain in early stages of development. This paper explains which steps, from concept over breadboard to laboratory work eventually led to the current design, construction and operation of a space greenhouse analogue in Antarctica, as main part of the EDEN ISS project, as well as the relevance for future space missions. The EDEN ISS project is led by SARA and comprises 13 academic, scientific and industrial partners from Europe and Canada. The consortium will design and test essential plant cultivation technologies using an International Standard Payload Rack form factor cultivation system for potential testing on-board the International Space Station. Furthermore, a Future Exploration Greenhouse will be designed with respect to future planetary bio-regenerative life support system deployments.

The project aims to conduct an analogue test campaign at the highly-isolated German Antarctic Neumayer Station III beginning in December 2017 with a duration of 12 months. A small and mobile container-sized test facility will be built in order to provide realistic mass flow relationships. In addition to technology

development and validation, food safety and plant handling procedures will be developed. These are integral aspects of the interaction between the crew and plants within closed environments.

The third branch, mainly intended to bolster the theoretical work with more practical insight into habitat design and operation is briefly presented in this paper: Analogue test site missions as conducted by the department in the Mars Desert Research Station in 2013 and 2014 as well as within NASA’s HI-SEAS 2 campaign in 2014. It will be explained how these missions helped with the design and development of the current hardware projects and the future research facility.

Overall the paper provides a comprehensive view of SARA’s activities within the field of future human spaceflight and exploration of the solar system, how these activities are interlinked, and their current outcome and results.

2 Incubator for Habitation

2.1 Background

Within DLR there is a long history of on-ground closed-loop habitation studies; for example the operation of the :envihab facility in Cologne [10] [22]. After the establishment of the DLR Institute of Space Systems in Bremen, the concept of a Facility of Laboratories for Sustainable Habitation (FLaSH) was initiated with preparatory work in cooperation with university student groups followed by a Concurrent Engineering (CE) feasibility study in 2011. The CE-process integrated the various disciplines — working collectively and in parallel — at the same site and facilitated the habitat design in the most efficient and consistent way. It was a guided process with access to a shared database and direct verbal and medial communication between all subsystem experts and therefore has been the perfect choice for the design of such a complex venture like FLaSH [5].

FLaSH’s objectives, summarized in Tab.1, were mainly the testing and qualification of different innovative technologies for systems and modules for space and terrestrial application. This was followed by testing the concept of a fully self-reliant artificial human habitat, public outreach for exploration and urban application, as well as the simulation of planetary exploration missions [23]. In subsequent years, the concept was further developed to a EU research proposal of a so-called Incubator for Habitation. The proposal regards a design

FIGURE 1. *The current design of the incubator central facility, image credit: Dr. Ondrej Doule (Space Innovations).*

study that would lead to a finished facility design beyond the current feasibility level of the study.

2.2 Design Overview

The general idea of the incubator for habitation is the design of a research facility, which offers the science community a common test environment to conduct cutting-edge research for sustainable human habitation. A preliminary layout of that incubator can be seen in Fig. 1. A dome structure is surrounded by a number of modules, housing the subsystems responsible for all necessary habitat functions. All modules are interconnected so that the flow of materials (e.g. air, water, waste, edible biomass) can be exchanged between the modules (sized $6 \times 6 \times 10 \text{ m}^3$). Furthermore there are office areas integrated into the design as well as public outreach constructions, e.g. a gallery for viewing the activities within the habitat (under observation of crew privacy).

In difference to the ordinary modules, the living module has three instead of two floors, with a glass cover

allowing horizon view for the crew, to reduce the crew stress. There are movable protective covers for all modules, sheltering them against weather and other possible outer influences.

The modular approach allows the highest level of flexibility in subsystems and system research, especially considering the long-term strategy of this infrastructure. Research areas and further habitat additions (to allow tests and simulations for terrestrial and space applications) are foreseen to be connected to a control centre. The life support modules follow a twofold principle where physical/chemical systems form the backbone, guaranteeing a certain reliability and safety, as well as the function as a backup strategy. A primary bio-regenerative life support system (LSS) on top of the traditional LSS (including algae, higher plants, and animals) enables a further closure of the different loops.

By sealing off the test facility, the closed-loop situation is generated. Human crews can test (similar to e.g. MARS 500) the living and working situation

Objective-No.	Description
MI-OJ-0010	Testing the concept of a fully self-reliant artificial human habitat
MI-OJ-0020	Simulation of planetary exploration missions
MI-OJ-0030	Testing and qualification of different innovative technologies for systems and modules for space and terrestrial application
MI-OJ-0040	Public outreach for exploration and urban application

TABLE 1. *Mission objectives of the Incubator for Habitation.*

in this environmentally-closed facility through several campaigns acting as the literally vital part of the habitation system. This infrastructure will offer a wide research spectrum for universities, research institutes and the industry in general where they can implement and test their own developed systems and technologies in relation to other habitat- and exploration technologies. Relevant areas are:

- Recycling and Conditioning (Air, Water, Waste),
- High-Tech farming (Agriculture, Animal Husbandry),
- Human Safety and Comfort (Living Module, Food Processing, Mobile Medical Care),
- Sustainable Resource Utilization and Advanced Manufacturing,
- Energy Redistribution and Storage,
- Automation and Control.

Acting as a focal point for this kind of research, the incubator's research infrastructure will also be capable of, and be tasked with, attracting and enabling research entities to participate within this field, even if they normally have no ties with the space sector.

The requirements for the design have been the accommodation of a 6 to 8 person crew for one year as well as a short term (2 weeks, simulating a resupply cargo vessel arriving) crew extension to up to 12 persons. The design has to provide a 95% closed-loop cycle, the remaining 5% of resources have to be suppliable by (simulated) ISRU activities. Up to 90% of all consumer products and 30% of spare parts are to be produced within the habitat itself, to achieve a reduced amount of resupply. The facility has to have a modular layout, which allows exchange of technology and systems and has to be designed for a minimum life-time of 20 years. Each module consists of an inner and outer part. The

latter is the shell that separates the facility from the outer environment, the inner part holds the actual systems and can be extended to be accessed (while not in a simulation).

In order to size the various subsystems for loop-closure, a matrix tool has been invented, which calculates and documents in- and outgoing material fluxes, e.g. oxygen, hydrogen and waste water, within the model habitat. How single subsystem outputs and demands fit together in the overall system is covered by the so called Material Trade Matrix, where the sum of the budgets of each module material flux is created. As soon as all material sums equal zero, the habitat loop is closed [21]. In Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 the Habitat Matrix is shown for the demands and the output of the individual modules. These figures would be summarized in the Trade Matrix to indicate any material with a lack or overproduction and thus perturbing the closed loop. The materials have been identified by the study team. For example, it becomes apparent that the Greenhouse Module has a demand of 46 kg of fertilizer, which can be produced by the Waste Module by recycling.

In addition to the technological topics, public participation and education are a central part of the idea behind the incubator for habitation: e.g. trainings and workshops on how the individual impact can be reduced now, which technologies are already helping with that and e.g. participating schools can contribute with small projects or experiments to the effort of the incubator. It is also envisioned to allow visitors the observation of the crew and experiments through the central glass-dome without disturbing them or altering the illusion of an off-Earth mission, see Fig. 1.

2.3 Terrestrial Application

The intended facility design allows the coordinated research of various industry and science partners with the

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Parameter Demand	Air Module	Animal Module	Food Processing Facility	Greenhouse Module	ISRU Module	Living Module	Sickbay	Waste Module	Water Module	Workshop Module
total anorganic solid waste demand in kg/day	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1,79	0	0
total C6H12O6 demand in kg/day	0	6,45	34,84	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
total CH4 demand in kg/day	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3,45	0
total CO2 demand in kg/day	60,58	0	0	16,45	0	0	0	0	0	0,01
total drinking water demand in kg/day	24,78	960,48	50	0	0	153,6	0	23	0,5	10
total Evaporated Water demand in kg/day	28,10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
total fertilizer demand in kg/day	0	0	0	46	0	0	0	0	0	0
total food demand in kg/day	0	0	28,15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
total green water demand in kg/day	0	0	0	720	0	0	0	0	1	0
total grey water demand in kg/day	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	554,48	0
total H2 demand in kg/day	0	0	0	0	1,13	0	0	0	0	0
total liquid waste demand in kg/day	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	60	2405	0
total Mars atmosphere output in kg/day	0	0	0	0	20	0	0	0	0	0
total Mars soil demand in kg/day	0	0	0	0	105	0	0	0	0	0
total O2 demand in kg/day	0	34,4	0	0	0	6,56	0	2,58	15	0,70
total organic solid waste demand in kg/day	0	92,92	0	0	0	0	0	15	0	0
total regolith demand in kg/day	0	0	0	0	405	0	0	0	0	0
total trace gas demand in kg/day	0	5,0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
total yellow water demand in kg/day	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	12,92	0	0
total ... demand in kg/day	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

FIGURE 2. Demands within the Habitat Matrix as applied during the FLaSH study.

Parameter Output	Air Module	Animal Module	Food Processing Facility	Greenhouse Module	ISRU Module	Living Module	Sickbay	Waste Module	Water Module	Workshop Module
total anorganic solid waste output in kg/day	0	0	0	0	454	0	0	0	0	1,79
total Ar output in kg/day	0	0	0	0	0,08	0	0	0	0	0
total C6H12O6 output in kg/day	41,30	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
total CH4 output in kg/day	0	0	0	0	1,81	0	0	3,45	0	0
total CH4 output in kg/day	0	0	0	0	1,81	0	0	3,45	0	0
total CO output in kg/day	0	0	0	0	6,37	0	0	0	0	0
total CO2 output in kg/day	0	52,1	0,6	0	4,76	8	0	5,54	10,8	0
total drinking water output in kg/day	0	0	0	557,71	17,15	0	0	0	560,48	0
total Evaporated Water output in kg/day	0	8,5	6,8	0	0	14,45	0	0	0,4	0
total fertilizer output in kg/day	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	46	0	0
total food output in kg/day	0	2,35	0	26,35	0	0	0	0	0	0
total green water output in kg/day	0	720	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
total grey water output in kg/day	28,10	240	43,2	123,81	0	58,72	0	51,92	0	5
total H2 output in kg/day	0	0	0	0	0,01	0	0	0,014	0	0
total liquid waste output in kg/day	0	0	0	0	0	60	0	0	2400	5
total N2 output in kg/day	0	0	0	0	0,1	0	0	0	0	0
total O2 output in kg/day	44,06	0	0	11,96	36,82	0	0	0	0	0
total oil/brine output in kg/day	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0,5	0
total organic solid waste output in kg/day	0	0	33,5	57,63	0	1,8	0	15	0	0
total raw materials output in kg/day	0	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	0
total trace gas output in kg/day	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	0
total yellow water output in kg/day	0	0	0	0	0	12,92	0	0	0	0
total ... output in kg/day	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

FIGURE 3. Outputs within the Habitat Matrix as applied during the FLaSH study.

common goal of developing technology for more efficient and resource-saving living. While the 'living' is initially intended to be off-planet, the research milestones can and should be used to create similar effects for living on Earth. Using a centralized research installation for the maturation of such processes and technologies allows the creation of synergy effects and of awareness of potential cooperation within the relevant community and of options for contribution for entities which have previously not been aware of their relevance for this area of technology and science.

While in space resources are scarce whereas on Earth resources (e.g. water) can be found in more abundance, at least locally. For space missions critical resources need to be either transferred into orbit and to the mission des-

tinuation or extracted at that destination; this has yet to be demonstrated. The larger the effort for this transfer (usually proportional to the distance from Earth), the larger the usefulness of an effective recycling of resources (e.g. turning used water into fresh water). Space based living and processes, e.g. food production, intended to be sustainable for a longer duration and less dependent on Earth resupply vehicles, consequently have to have a large efficiency or recycling rate. An extended human presence drives the demands of the corresponding technologies, systems and processes up. Applying these technologies, systems and processes on Earth can however eventually lead to improved efficiency of living on Earth. This means the incubator can lead to changes in processes, practices, and structures to moderate damages

or to benefit from opportunities associated with climate change, urban development and environmentally difficult regions on Earth, e.g. deserts. Finally it can help to reduce the ecological footprint of the human population whilst maintaining and promoting the health and performance in today's society.

2.4 Further Development of the Concept

Currently the incubator's feasibility has been investigated and confirmed in the described study work by setting up basic layouts and budgets for its operation and construction. At the moment a proposal for a EU funded project is prepared within the Horizon 2020 programme, which after three years will culminate in a complete design of the facility. This includes a cost estimate, a legal framework for its operation and a network of research and industry partners for its utilization. The final step would encompass the actual construction and subsequent use of the facility, which is currently not estimated to happen before 2020.

3 Greenhouse for Antarctica and Space

3.1 Background

Recent achievements in growing plants on-board the International Space Station (ISS) have shown once again that plant cultivation in space is possible and beneficial to the living conditions of the crew. However, a review of plant production facilities flown in space shows such systems are limited in size and biomass production. The plant growth chambers operated on various spacecraft and stations so far have been built with the main purpose of doing science in space and not for being part of the life support system. [24]

Testing large plant cultivation systems as part of a bio-regenerative life support system in space is mainly limited by the size of such systems, their energy consumption and the inexperience in operating them. Consequently, in the past different research groups and organizations relied on ground-based testing. Facilities such as, the Japanese Closed Ecology Experiment Facility (CEEFF) [16], the Russian Bios facilities [9], NASA's Biomass Production Chamber (BPC) [11], the Chinese Lunar Palace 1 [7] and Biosphere 2 [14] have investigated the cultivation of plants in closed environments and even in closed ecology life support systems.

Those facilities were all part of larger research complexes which included laboratories, workshops and a

large number of maintenance personnel. Testing life support systems and in particular plant cultivation technologies at analogue test sites with realistic mass flows has been suggested by researchers and organizational studies alike [12]. Some greenhouse systems have been deployed at analogue test sites such as the Arthur Clarke Mars Greenhouse in the Haughton crater in the Canadian Arctic [2], the Greenhab at the Mars Desert Research Station (MDRS) in Utah, USA [19] and the South Pole Food Growth Chamber (SPFGC) [18] at the US South Pole Station in Antarctica.

Within the wide range of analogue test sites (e.g. remote locations, deserts, polar regions) Antarctica has a number of conditions which make the continent predestined for life support testing and validation campaigns [6]. Those conditions are:

- Crew size,
- crew dynamics,
- inhospitable environment,
- technology dependency,
- extremely low biodiversity environment,
- similar habitat interfaces.

The long heritage of Antarctic greenhouses [3] substantiates that plant growth in Antarctic stations is possible and desired by the crew on-site. Consequently, Antarctica has been chosen as the primary target to test and validate plant cultivation technologies for future space missions by SARA.

In 2011 the EDEN (Evolution and Design of Environmentally-Closed Nutrition Sources) research group was created by SARA to focus on enhancing plant cultivation technologies for food production in space. From the beginning, one of the primary goals was the design, deployment and operation of a greenhouse module at an analogue test site, preferably in Antarctica, which eventually culminated in the EDEN ISS project.

3.2 EDEN ISS

EDEN ISS is a research project in the European Horizon 2020 framework. It consists of 13 research organizations, universities, SMEs and large industry partners from six countries in Europe and Canada. The project officially started in March 2015 and will last until the end of 2018. The main goal of EDEN ISS is:

The adaptation, integration, fine-tuning and demonstration of higher plant cultivation technologies and operation procedures for safe food production on-board ISS and for future human space exploration missions.

It is further divided into three project phases regarding the creation of a greenhouse system:

1. Design phase (March 2015 - March 2016)
2. Hardware development phase (March 2016 - October 2017)
3. Antarctic campaign phase (October 2017 - December 2018)

A more detailed project overview and description can be found on the project website [1] and in [25].

Design Overview

The EDEN ISS greenhouse facility is designed to provide fresh produce for overwintering crews at the Neumayer III Antarctic station while at the same time advancing the readiness of a number of plant growth technologies (including a full ISPR, International Standard Payload Rack, plant cultivation system demonstrator) and operational procedures. The greenhouse will be located approximately 200 m south of the Neumayer Station III Antarctic research station.

The actual facility consists of two high cube shipping containers with a length of 6 m (20 ft), which will be placed on top of an external platform. The greenhouse is subdivided into three distinct sections, as shown in Figure 4:

- Cold porch: a small room providing storage and a small air buffer to limit the entry of cold air when the main entrance door of the facility is utilized.
- Service Section: houses the primary control, air management, thermal control and nutrient delivery systems of the greenhouse as well as the ISPR plant cultivation system.
- Future Exploration Greenhouse (FEG): the main plant growth area of the greenhouse facility, including multilevel plant growth racks operating in a precisely controlled environment.

Figure 5 shows a technical drawing of the complete facility. The image shows the preliminary design without

outer side walls and roof.

The complete facility has a footprint of 29.5 m² (outer dimensions) and a usable inside area of roughly 25 m². The FEG makes up around half of the facility and contains the main plant production space. The plant growth area is arranged in a shelf configuration with up to four levels of cultivation area. In its current configuration the FEG has a total cultivation area of roughly 12.5 m².

EDEN ISS focuses on the cultivation of pick-and-eat vegetables which can only be stored for a few days. During the Antarctic campaign the following crops will be grown: various types of lettuce, dwarf tomatoes, cucumbers, bell peppers, radishes, strawberries, spinach, swiss chard, red mustard, chives, coriander, mint, parsley and basil. The objective is to have enough yield to provide a fresh mixed salad to the overwintering crew every week. Figure 6 shows the current allocation of crops within the shelf-like cultivation system of the FEG.

Crop selection was conducted via an evaluation developed by researchers from Wageningen University and Research in the Netherlands [8]. The method evaluates crops based on the categories yield, production and quality. The category yield has the subcriteria harvest index, space per time efficiency and light energy use efficiency. Commercially available seeds, maximum growth height, suitability for production system, required light intensity, first harvest time, disease resistance, reasonable shelf life, minimum handling time and spread harvest are the subcriteria in the category production. The category quality is divided into the subcriteria edible plant parts, ready-to-eat after harvest, texture, taste, pungency and appearance.

3.3 Mission in Antarctica and Beyond

The research and validation campaign in Antarctica will start in December 2017 when the greenhouse arrives at the Neumayer III research station. After setting up the greenhouse and performing an overall system test the plant cultivation will start in January 2018. For the initial two months of the expedition three members of the EDEN team will go to Antarctica. From February to December 2018 one EDEN team member will stay over winter together with a crew of engineers, scientists, a doctor and a cook (nine in total) at the Neumayer III station.

During the Antarctic campaign, the following datasets will be collected for research:

FIGURE 4. Overview of the EDEN ISS greenhouse main elements

Plant Cultivation Data

A large dataset associated with the growth of the selected crops destined for the EDEN ISS greenhouse will be generated during laboratory tests and the research campaign in Antarctica.

Greenhouse Operations Data

Datasets will be collected twice, once during test deployment, once during the operation phase. Data contains greenhouse environmental, system health and imaging data and can be used for comparison with other comparable plant production systems.

ISPR Cultivation System Operations Data

Collected three times, during testing, test deployment and operation. The data contains full-rack demonstrator environmental data, system health as well as imaging data.

Food Quality and Safety Data

Will be collected during assembly, testing and during operation in Antarctica. Determined by chemical composition (e.g. type of carbohydrates) and consumer perception.

Microbial Investigations Data

Sampling will occur on surfaces to gain an overview

of the diversity and physiological capability of micro-organisms under different growth conditions (e.g. different temperatures).

Effects on Crew Data

Analysis of crew mood, workability and cohesion.

The datasets will be evaluated by the EDEN ISS project team and according to the rules of the European Horizon 2020 research framework they will be openly accessible to the research community.

4 Analogue Testing

4.1 Background

Starting in early 2013 SARA began to conduct research campaigns at analogue test sites, namely the Mars Desert Research Station (MDRS) in Utah, USA [15], see Fig. 8, and the Hawaii Space Exploration Analog and Simulation (HI-SEAS) on Hawaii, USA [20]. Beginning with a precursor mission for preparation of plant experiments and for habitat design one member of the department was part of MDRS' Crew 125 in early 2013 and one year later a second scientist took part in Crew 135, and likewise in HI-SEAS Crew 2, for plant growth experiments. Furthermore, other members of SARA

FIGURE 5. CAD drawing of the EDENISS greenhouse with the cold porch and service section to the right and the FEG to the left.

have taken part in analogue test site missions as well. The previously described Antarctica mission will further add to the general knowledge of living and working in an artificial habitation situation, adding insight for design and development of such systems.

4.2 Mission Objectives

MDRS Crew 125

MDRS Crew 125 was the second rotation of the EuroMoonMars campaign and lasted for two weeks. The general mission objectives ranged from several geological research experiments in the Utah desert, e.g. investigating life traces conservation [4, 17], to human factors research and technological experiments [4]. The latter was part of SARA's investigation. First of all the exact situation at MDRS was investigated to prepare interfaces, location and handling of a future plant growth experiment. The second objective for SARA's participation was the review on MDRS' design and layout to draw conclusion for the habitat design work of the department. This served to incorporate 'lessons learnt'

into the design considerations before actually building an own habitat research station.

MDRS Crew 135 and HI-SEAS 2

The participation on Crew 135 was under the auspice of furthering the greenhouse equipment at MDRS. Overall Crew 135 was investigating the reliability of the mechanics, structure and power supply of the habitat as well as improving the illumination and automation of the station's greenhouse module. Besides that it was SARA's objective to install an artificial illumination system in MDRS' greenhouse and experiment with its contribution to plant growth by comparing growth with and without artificial illumination. Furthermore the greenhouse was reviewed regarding its properties, e.g. watering automation and thermal insulation, for recommendations on improvement.

During HI-SEAS Crew 2 mission the experiments were extensions of the plant experiments conducted during MDRS Crew 135 and focussed on the comparison of plant growth improvement of various illumination systems and their properties. The plants grown were let-

FIGURE 6. Allocation of crops to the different cultivation units within the FEG. Green boxes indicate the growth trays. Add-on crops: Radish, strawberry, spinach, swiss chard, red mustard. Herbs: Chives, parsley, coriander, basil.

tuce and radish.

4.3 Results and Impact

MDRS Crew 125

At the time of this crew rotation, MDRS had been in operation for more than 10 years. While wear-off of various components was detectable, it did not hinder the operation of the station. The most considerable wear-off was the condition of the outer airlock doors, as shown in Fig. 7. Both of them were significantly misaligned, which made closure and opening difficult. The hinges were under stress and had decayed to a point where they lost screws (likely due to rust and dynamic loads). During strong winds the door was pulled on very strongly and crashed into the hinges. Generally, the doors were the major wear-off element in the whole habitat. It is proposed to apply sliding doors (comparable to transport vehicles) and mount rails on the habitat walls on future facilities and also use sliding doors for I4H. Sliding doors would have three advantages:

- No dynamic loads on the door itself and its mounting,
- no area which can be attacked by wind forces,

- the door can be opened independently of the relative pressure from out- and inside.

FIGURE 7. Left: The closed outer engineering airlock door with hinges on its right and no support on its left side. Right: One of the bottom hinges, strongly constructed, but decay and likely dynamic forces caused the loss of a screw.

The large amount of utensils used in MDRS (especially for various experiments and also supply storage) suggest the need for more storage room. Certain elements could likely be stowed away in the ceilings of the rooms, as there is a strong steel beam structure, which

is currently unused. Also an actual protocol for inventory and removing unusable elements from the inventory could help reduce the amount of required storage space and the time needed for locating the equipment.

There are two issues that regard the stateroom condition: extensive heat and lack of outside view.

There is enough room to have privacy and live relatively comfortably but the air flow within the rooms is minimal. Hot air is introduced via a venting system, creating a warm and dry atmosphere, which especially is disadvantageous for sleeping. As a result, crewmembers tend to sleep with open doors, which exposes them to the noise of the overall station venting system and water pump. Therefore effective and noise reduced venting measures need to be implemented in an actual habitat.

Windows in the staterooms would also add crew comfort. While these would introduce structural, radiation and heating problems in actual flight-hardware, these issues could be redeemed. Windows would also relax power demand as daylight removes the need for artificial illumination.

A more detailed description and analysis of the Mars Desert Research Station can be found in [13]. The proposed improvements are intended for application in the incubator for habitation.

FIGURE 8. MDRS with the main habitat (back) and greenhouse (front) during Crew 125's rotation.

MDRS Crew 135

The plant growth experiments conducted at MDRS showed the viability of using artificial light sources for improved plant growth properties. Within the 14 days rotation it was shown that depending on the plant age,

lettuce could increase its fresh mass by between 11% and 34% when exposed to artificial illumination for 12 hours opposed to 10.5 hours of natural light for the control group. Similarly, the hypocotyl length was reduced by 20 to 28%, which is a sign for improved growth conditions. Consequently artificial illumination - without draining the power supply of MDRS significantly - has been recommended to MDRS management for improving the station's Greenhab efficiency, especially for crews in the early parts of the season, where natural illumination is scarce.

Furthermore Crew 135 made the recommendation to use plastic shelves, instead of wooden because of wear-off and risks of splinters. Also an automated watering system was proposed for reducing the time constraints of watering plants for the crew. Similarly a simple temperature control system would allow creating more suitable growth conditions for most plants, removing the large temperature variation from 0°C in the morning to 35°C during sunny days. More detail can be found in [13].

HI-SEAS Crew 2

The artificial illumination experiments showed the dependence of fresh mass and hypocotyl length on illumination wavelength for radishes and lettuce. While red and blue light provided the best results in terms of hypocotyl length for radishes, it led to the least amount of fresh mass. Best results (improved by a factor of 1.5 to 1.8) were obtained with white light, suggesting that a combination of white and blue or red light would lead to optimal results concerning radishes. For lettuce the hypocotyl length did not show a significant variation based on illumination wavelength, but influenced the leaf mass, which was largest for red and blue lighting, i.e. about a factor 1.3 larger than for white light.

Secondary results of the mission have been that all crewmembers, even though previously not familiar with plant care, valued the inclusion of plants in the habitat and caring for them. The latter took about 15 minutes per average per day. A detailed description of these experiments and their results can be found in [20].

Lessons Learnt

As mentioned before the major motivation for the analogue missions conducted by SARA have been possible impact the respective experience provides regarding the habitat and greenhouse design and their oper-

FIGURE 9. Research path for terrestrial and space habitation.

ational processes. For instance, the door mechanisms and living quarter design as reviewed at MDRS will influence the design of the I4H's living quarters and outer doors. The procedures reviewed during greenhouse operation at MDRS and HI-SEAS will further procedures of EDEN ISS and its design.

5 Future Research

With the help of the incubator for habitation and the already maturing greenhouse technology, the research path is at a step where technology testing can occur in an integrated manner, as described in Section 2. However the idea is to eventually separate the research paths into their domains, namely space and terrestrial application, as depicted in Fig. 9. While the first step is intended to allow the qualification and validation of the respective technologies (e.g. air management or plant

cultivation), the second step will be directed at optimizing the designs to their specific purpose and with the validated technology approaches. For the space path this means reduction of mass and power demands, and integration into a real simulation environment to actually test such a planet-based habitat before applying it to a lunar or martian outpost. Likewise for the terrestrial path, the next steps would be to incorporate and test these technologies into larger scale applications, e.g. the food production technology for vertical farming in urban areas, and decentralize them, e.g. water recycling in individual households of a city. The respective next step would be the actual application-ready design, i.e. an actual habitat on another planetary body or serial production and usage of technology that is capable of reducing the human ecological foot-print in everyday life. With the help of the incubator for habitation and the already maturing greenhouse technology, the research path is

at a step where technology testing can occur in an integrated manner, as described in Section 2. However the idea is to eventually separate the research paths into their domains, namely space and terrestrial application, as depicted in Fig. 9. While the first step is intended to allow the qualification and validation of the respective technologies (e.g. air management or plant cultivation), the second step will be directed at optimizing the designs to their specific purpose and with the validated technology approaches. For the space path this means reduction of mass and power demands, and integration into a real simulation environment to actually test such a planet-based habitat before applying it to a lunar or martian outpost. Likewise for the terrestrial path, the next steps would be to incorporate and test these technologies into larger scale applications, e.g. the food production technology for vertical farming in urban areas, and to decentralize them, e.g. water recycling in individual households of a city. The next respective step would be the actual application-ready design, i.e. an actual habitat on another planetary body or serial production and usage of technology that is capable of reducing the human ecological foot-print in everyday life.

Concerning a timeframe, the building of the incubator is not foreseen to happen before 2020, whereas a dedicated space simulation habitat - requiring research results gained from the incubator's operation - is not expected before 2030. However its own operation will - because most systems will only be optimized and not specifically developed from scratch - likely produce the necessary results faster, i.e. the construction of an actual habitat for space could happen in the 2030s.

6 Conclusion and Outlook

The authors have shown the different paths taken by SARA to further the development of sophisticated habitation and greenhouse technology. It has been elaborated how habitation technology also has an impact on human ecological footprint on Earth and how design work can be enhanced and improved by analogue test site missions.

Currently SARA plans to improve the recent design for its habitation laboratory within a European Union funded project in the Research Infrastructure Call of 2016. Part of the proposed project is the complete technical design of the facility, but also of legal and operational processes behind the research.

The EDEN ISS project will advance the current

state of plant cultivation in space through ground-based demonstration of key technologies. The demonstration of plant cultivation in a large-scale facility at the Neumayer III Station in Antarctica acts as a precursor for future experiments on ISS and strengthens the development of technologies for future missions to Moon and Mars. EDEN ISS will generate and provide scientific data to the whole bio-regenerative life support community.

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